

Requirements for Completion of the Ramp-Up Phase

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Disclaimer:

This document refers to the status of Base4NFDI's developments in Spring 2026. Many aspects are still under discussion, particularly with regard to the scope and functionalities of the upcoming NFDI service portfolio, which will affect workflows and responsibilities. Any adjustments to these will be addressed in revised versions of this document.

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1. Purpose

This document serves as a **common framework** for the Ramp-Up Phase of your basic service. The paper corresponds to the one already published for the Integration Phase¹ and follows on from what is explained there. It applies to all basic services and their proposals as of February 2026 and later.

In order to facilitate reading, the main actors are abbreviated as follows:

- The **service team** designs and builds the service and will be supported by Base4NFDI staff:²
- **SER**: The Service Stewards support the everyday development activities with their domain-specific expertise.
- **TA2**: Task Area 2 / Service Integration and Ramping up for Operation supports quality assurance and integration of the service into the upcoming NFDI service portfolio.
- **TA3**: Task Area 3 / Service Coherence Processes and Monitoring guides with respect to the overall Base4NFDI processes and the cooperation with the NFDI sections.
- **TA4**: Task Area 4 / Project Governance aids with all aspects of outreach, training, and evaluation.

2. Scope of ramp-up

The **two-year** Ramp-Up Phase marks the transition from foundational setup to full operational capacity. While the Initialisation and Integration Phases were dedicated to establishing a cohesive and interoperable Basic Service concept, this final stage focuses on optimising and finalising the service and its components. This includes a consistent exchange with and an onboarding of further communities and, if required, adaptations of the service to their requirements. The Ramp-Up Phase prepares the services for reliable, secure, sustainable, and scalable operation. It is expected that the user base will be expanded to other consortia and institutions during the Ramp-Up Phase.

At the end of the phase, the service is fully functional and compliant with relevant legal regulations, in the first place with GDPR. Any required security, backup, and protection measures are in place to ensure the integrity and availability of both service and data. There is an outline of the organisational form of the service operation, and the costs of its provision have been quantified. Interoperability has been further advanced to connect the service to the NFDI service portfolio and federate it with other entities, especially EOSC. This translates into several tasks to be completed and delivered by the service teams as detailed below.

In short, “ramped up” can therefore be defined as “finalised, sustained, and secure”.

¹ Requirements for completion of integration phase, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17107044>

² <https://base4nfdi.de/about/people>

To this end, there are **six mandatory deliverables** from Base4NFDI and **three conditionally required ones**. All deliverables and their results must be documented in the Base4NFDI project management software OpenProject. Base4NFDI will provide corresponding work packages and templates for the basic service teams. Please utilise the support offered by the Base4NFDI team (TA2, SERs) if you encounter any difficulties.

At the end of the Ramp-Up Phase, Base4NFDI states to what extent the deliverables have been met. The OpenProject tasks, including attached or linked materials, are treated as part of the project record and are archived accordingly. Based on this, Base4NFDI informs the Consortia Assembly and the Scientific Senate³ about the completion of the phase.

3. Timeline and responsibilities

The following Figure 1 represents what is to be done by **Base4NFDI** (framed beige in diagram below) and **service teams** (green) during the Ramp-Up Phase. The service team's own work plan, tasks, and deliverables mark the starting and pivotal point of these activities. This is mapped to nine Ramp-Up Phase deliverables. D.RUp.1-7 relate directly to the development of the service and are shown in Figure 1 (D.RUp.8-9 concern general participation issues in Base4NFDI and are omitted here). All deliverables are explained individually below. The fulfillment of these deliverables is tracked by respective OpenProject tasks. We strongly recommend using OpenProject regularly throughout the Ramp-Up Phase to document results as they become available.

Figure 1. Scheme of a service team's (green) and Base4NFDI's (beige) collaboration in the Ramp-Up Phase

³ <https://www.nfdi.de/association/bodies/?lang=en>

All requirements shown above are due at the **end of the Ramp-Up Phase**, with the following exceptions:

1. Month 15: If the Scientific Senate raised any specific questions or tasks prior to the Ramp-Up Phase, these need to be answered or addressed in an **interim report** to the Senate.
2. Before month 18: A consultation with Base4NFDI on suitable organisational models.

The following **Table 1** illustrates the timeline of the Ramp-Up Phase, along with regular tasks listed at the bottom. It outlines when interim reports, consultations, and assessments must be completed. Service teams should continuously update the corresponding OpenProject tasks, as these entries form the basis for the final phase assessment. The due dates refer to a Ramp-Up Phase of two years. If the Ramp-Up phase is shorter than the intended 24 months, delivery dates have to be adjusted accordingly. This will be done in bi-lateral communication between the service team and TA2.

Due until	Task	Responsibilities
Before applying for ramp-up	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Discussion of ramp-up concept in a section meeting • Consultation with Base4NFDI: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ ramp-up concept and respective responsibilities of service team and Base4NFDI ○ evaluation of necessity of quality and software assessments ○ check of applicability of tasks D.RUp.6-7 ○ discussion on the actual length of the phase and adaption of due dates 	<p>Service team: presentation of concept</p> <p>TA2: overview of Ramp-Up Phase</p> <p>SER: coordination</p>

After acceptance by the consortia assembly, before ramp-up	Collection of Scientific Senate's requirements	TA4: short discussion in Senate meeting SER: coordination and communication Base4NFDI staff: Collect questions and possible to-dos in OpenProject in D.RUp.5
Month 1	Ramp-up kick-off with Base4NFDI (TA2, TA3, SER)	TA2: presentation SER: coordination
Month 15	If there are specific requirements by the Scientific Senate (cf. above): Interim report (D.RUp.5), at the request of the Senate with an accompanying review of the TEC <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Answers and documented adjustments of the work plan in OpenProject 	Service team: writing Base4NFDI: submission to the Scientific Senate
Before month 18	Consultation with TA2 and decision on an organisational model	TA2: provide drafted candidate models
Month 22–23	3rd self-assessment of software quality (if applicable / developed as part of the service)	Service team: fill in questionnaire TA2: provide questionnaire and write report
Month 22–23	Preparation of final reports on adoption, interoperability, success stories, quality, sustainability, maturity, security, and legal compliance	Service team

Month 24	Check of fulfilment of portfolio-relevant requirements	TA2
Month 24	Brief report on the achievements of the phase and the final state of service development. Collection and joint export of OpenProject documentation, including any other relevant documentation. Publication of the report on the Base4NFDI web pages and forwarding of the results to the consortia assembly and the Scientific Senate.	Service team: report Base4NFDI: Confirmation of completeness, collection of documentation, publication, and provision to NFDI bodies.
After month 24	Presentation of the results in a section meeting, announcement of the successful completion of the Ramp-Up Phase	Service team, Base4NFDI
After month 24	Inclusion of the service in the portfolio, after consent of the Scientific Senate	Base4NFDI
Monthly	Jour fixe with TA1 and TA2, SER, other teams	Base4NFDI
As needed	Consultations with TA2	Service team
Regularly	Contribution to the Base4NFDI service demonstrations and similar formats (recommended, optional)	Service team
Yearly/once	Participation in Base4NFDI User Conference and other outreach activities	Service team

Table 2 below maps the deliverables described in this document to the timeline explained above.

Deliverable Milestone	Type	Description	Due until
D.RUp.1	OpenProject tables	Report on service finalisation and maturity	M24
D.RUp.2	OpenProject	Legal compliance report	M24
D.RUp.3	OpenProject	Sustainability report, including organisational model	M24
D.RUp.4	OpenProject + Google table	Provision of service portfolio metadata	M24

Deliverable Milestone	Type	Description	Due until
D.RUp.5	OpenProject	Report to the Scientific Senate (if applicable)	M15
D.RUp.6	OpenProject + Google form	3rd self-assessment of software quality (if applicable)	M24
D.RUp.7	OpenProject + Google tables	User-centric documentation and training (if applicable)	M24
D.RUp.8	Presentation and report	Short overview about the outcomes of the Ramp-Up Phase and presentation in a section meeting	After M24
D.RUp.9	Presentations	Participation in Base4NFDI User Conference	As appropriate

TA2 will review and confirm the results in terms of content and plausibility (TA4 for D.RUp.8), together with the Service Stewards if necessary, while TA3 will do the same in terms of completeness. An export of the OpenProject tasks will formally document the fulfilment of the deliverables and the completion of the Ramp-Up Phase. It will be forwarded to the Consortia Assembly and the Scientific Senate for their decision on the inclusion of the service in the service portfolio.

4. Mandatory service-related deliverables

The following **four** deliverables from Base4NFDI are mandatory for all service teams to complete the Ramp-Up Phase. We suggest taking all these deliverables and milestones into account when writing your proposal work plan, and/or mapping your own deliverables and milestones to them. For each deliverable, Base4NFDI will create a corresponding reporting task in your OpenProject workspace, providing further instructions and a structure for documenting. Both publicly available and internal documents can be provided there as links or as text as needed. An export of your documentation in OpenProject is then sufficient as a report of the finalisation of the Ramp-Up Phase.

Deliverable D.RUp.1 Documentation of service finalisation, maturity, and usability

As defined above, the most essential goal of ramp-up is taking the service to its final intended maturity. This ensures its stable and performant operation in the real-world deployments of the service, a high efficiency, a consistent use, and a clear added value across contexts.

The service team is therefore asked to demonstrate the service's maturity in accordance with the use cases for which it was developed and to give plausible evidence, based on actual service employments, that

- all planned functionalities and components of the service have been developed in accordance with the service team's work plan, are working and being used as planned,
- all intended interfaces and connections to other services and systems are in place and working,
- components and interfaces are built in an interoperable manner upon open standards to accommodate further use cases, future expansion, and broader connectivity in the future,
- the user interface is intuitive and easy to use,⁴⁵
- users – especially those who joined after the Integration Phase – are successfully employing the service for the benefit of their work,
- there is a defined process and a clear documentation of how further institutions can employ the service in their own environment and workflows,
- there is an established feedback and control mechanism to deal with possibly arising problems and to trigger future improvements.

Documentation:

- For documenting measures and achievements, tables are prepared in the OpenProject task assigned to this deliverable. Any results shall be collected there.
- Evidence can include deployment records, onboarding/uptake reports, configuration notes, short usage summaries, already existing KPI and usage statistics, or other. These can be either incorporated directly into the OpenProject task or linked to it, as appropriate.
- For technical services, this can be done along the lines of the TRL concept.

Supported by Base4NFDI:

- Base4NFDI will support the teams with identifying relevant topics, applicable maturity-related aspects of the service, and their work programme, and coordinating documentation.

Due date: The final report is due at the end of the Ramp-Up Phase.

Deliverable D.RUp.2 Documentation of legal compliance and protection measures

This deliverable documents that the service is ready for sustained operation from a legal and data protection perspective. The focus is mainly on (i) intellectual property clarity and lawful use of third-party components, (ii) compliance with data protection regulations

⁴ See “Notes on usability”, published jointly with this document

⁵ Guidelines on Application of Web Accessibility, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15719660>

such as the GDPR, (iii) accessibility requirements, and (iv) the terms of use of the service. The service teams should be able to show that they understand what they are using, what they have developed, and how data is handled. This means that, from the technical finalisation of the service:

- The service team identifies the institution that holds primary legal responsibility for operating the service, including its role in relation to intellectual property ownership and data protection obligations.
- Ownership of all service components, software, documentation, and other results created by the team is clearly identified and documented.
- Licensing conditions for components are explicitly stated and compatible with the intended mode of operation and reuse. Guidance on selecting appropriate licenses and assessing compatibility is available in the Base4NFDI Service design guide document.⁶
- All personal and sensitive data processed by the service is identified, justified, minimised, and handled in accordance with applicable data protection law.
- Relevant data processing activities are documented at a level appropriate for the service, including information on data storage, access rights, and retention practices.
- Risks related to data protection and international data transfers are assessed and, where necessary, mitigated.
- Applicable accessibility requirements and implemented accessibility measures are identified and documented, and transparency about known limitations is provided where relevant.
- Applicable terms of use or user conditions for accessing the service are identified and referenced where the service is available to external users.

To explain the legal aspects outlined in this section at a level appropriate for the Ramp-Up Phase, more detailed information and, where applicable, extended analyses are provided in a supplemental document published together with this document.⁷

Documentation:

For documentation of compliance with legal regulations, tables for entering any relevant information have been prepared in the OpenProject task assigned to this deliverable.

Evidence may include policy summaries, structured tables, diagrams, or short explanatory texts. These can be included directly into the OpenProject task or linked to external documents, as appropriate. Each main documentation area includes a clear statement confirming whether the requirement applies or does not apply to the service.

If there is more than one service provider, the documentation must be given for any of them. If a specific requirement is not applicable, this should be stated explicitly.

Support by Base4NFDI:

⁶ Base4NFDI Service Design Guide, section 4.5.2.1, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16306726>

⁷ See “Notes on legal requirements”, published jointly with this document

- Base4NFDI will support the service teams by providing guidance on relevant legal and data protection topics, aligning documentation expectations, creating the documentation, and facilitating coordination with legal or data protection experts where necessary.

Due Date: All relevant information and applicable documentation is due at the end of the Ramp-Up Phase.

Deliverable D.RUp.3 Documentation of sustainable operational perspective

The Integration Phase should have delivered a drafted operational concept⁸ that specifies the resources required to operate the service and also names one (or more) future service providers. In the Ramp-Up Phase, the service team shall:

- develop and describe a sensible organisational model for the service, e. g., centralised, peer-to-peer, or federated,
- assess and, if necessary, revise the resource estimates from the integration phase,
- estimate costs and prices, relating to the current state of the service and possible expansions, the desired service availability (like 24/7 vs. usual business hours), and the expected user base (like a few experts vs. 100.000 students),
- provide written commitments from the intended operators.

These concepts should address a time span of at least five years after the Ramp-up Phase and have to be aligned with – or, ideally, covered by – the respective regulations and concepts of the service provider(s).

Documentation:

- The results should be published as part of the documentation and presented in a meeting of the respective section (see D.RUp.8 below).
- The publication and a respective link must be recorded in the OpenProject task of this deliverable.

Support by Base4NFDI:

- Base4NFDI will support the teams in identifying suitable concepts.

Due date: Until month 18, a consultation with TA2 to decide on a suitable organisational model is required. The organisational model is due at the end of the Ramp-Up Phase.

Deliverable D.RUp.4 Provision of service portfolio metadata

The portfolio metadata enables consistent presentation, comparison and maintenance of all services in a common service portfolio.⁹ It also ensures that essential information such

⁸ Requirements for completion of integration phase (D.Int.3).

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17107044>

⁹ See “Notes on portfolio requirements”, published jointly with this document

as capabilities, limitations, KPIs,¹⁰ provider roles and governance is available. Parts of this information have already been collected during the Integration Phase; the Ramp-Up Phase is concerned with completing the data set.

Documentation:

- Together with the Service Stewards and TA2 staff, the team must enter all required information in a prepared Google table, which is linked to the OpenProject task of this deliverable.
- The information will have to be provided directly in this table and should therefore be concise, comprehensible, and plausible with respect to the context of the service.
- For some topics, the table provides drop-down menus to choose from.

Support by Base4NFDI:

- TA2 and the Service Stewards will help to map the results of the teams to the portfolio-relevant metadata and record all required information.

Due date: All metadata and descriptions are due at the end of the Ramp-Up Phase. but should be entered in the table as soon as they become available.

5. Mandatory – if applicable – service-related deliverables

The following **three** deliverables are mandatory for all service teams to complete the Ramp-Up Phase, if they are applicable to their service. This will be discussed and assessed in the pre-phase consultation with Base4NFDI. We suggest taking into account all of these deliverables and milestones when writing your proposal work plan, and/or mapping your own deliverables and milestones to them.

Deliverable D.RUp.5 Report to the Scientific Senate

The Scientific Senate may come up with questions or even requirements regarding the service and the team’s work plan before the Ramp-Up Phase. These topics and possible tasks will be collected and provided by Base4NFDI in the respective OpenProject task of this deliverable right away.

Documentation:

- Whenever a question has been answered, a topic resolved, or a task completed, this needs to be documented in the OpenProject task according to the issues collected there.
- Finally, an OpenProject export will serve as a report to the Senate.

Support by Base4NFDI:

¹⁰ See “Notes on KPIs”, published jointly with this document

- The Scientific Senate’s questions and requirements will be collected and provided to the service teams by Base4NFDI. Base4NFDI will give a short service presentation to the Scientific Senate after the submission of the Ramp-Up proposal.
- Base4NFDI will support the teams in addressing issues and adapting the work plan, if necessary.

Due date: The report to the Scientific Senate is due by month 15.

Deliverable D.RUp.6 Self-assessment of software quality

With respect to code that the teams develop themselves – if any –, there have been two self-assessments of software quality already in the Integration Phase.¹¹ A final one must be conducted in the Ramp-Up Phase.

Documentation:

- Again, the assessment results will be collected through a form provided by TA2.
- The completion of this must be documented in the associated OpenProject task.

Support by Base4NFDI:

- TA2 provides a checklist of relevant quality criteria the service teams are asked to fill in.
- TA2 will help figuring out which parts of the assessment are relevant.

Due date: The assessment will be due at the end of the Ramp-Up Phase.

Deliverable D.RUp.7 User-centred documentation and training

User-centered documentation and training is an essential foundation for user adoption of any service. While in the Integration Phase documentation and training material is created and piloted, the Ramp-Up Phase focuses on

- Long-term user adoption
- Continuous maintenance of documentation and training
- Roll-out planning of training for the wider audience
- Sustainable plan for onboarding and supporting new and existing users
- Sustainable plan for documentation and training in the future
- Further measures to support adoption as needed
- Integration concept with support/service desk

¹¹ See “Notes on software quality”, published jointly with this document

Training activities should be considered mandatory, if applicable, as in rare cases, a service might not require training activities. The activities listed here should be part of the Ramp-Up Phase planning but can be adapted to the training needs as required.

Documentation of activities:

- Open Educational Resources are tracked in the respective reporting sheet of Base4NFDI.
- Educational Events are tracked in the respective reporting sheet of Base4NFDI.
- Deliverables for training and documentation are to be mapped/added in the OpenProject task of D.RUp.7 as applicable. There is no extra report for training necessary besides the own deliverables planned by the service as part of their work programme – meaning if the service includes training and documentation deliverables that cover the above-mentioned activities, it is sufficient to reference those.

Support by Base4NFDI:

- The training task force, consisting of one or more service team members, the services Service Steward and the Base4NFDI Training Manager, is scheduled regularly based on service needs (e. g., every 4–6 weeks). This is highly recommended and has proven valuable for teams in all phases.
- The Base4NFDI Training Manager coordinates training activities, provides feedback and quality assurance and assists with planning and effort estimations. They also provide knowledge transfer and consulting and identify best practices and synergies across services and with other RDM initiatives.
- Service Stewards assist with their domain-specific knowledge and by facilitating collaboration with (future) users across NFDI consortia.

Due date: The documentation of activities on “user-centric documentation and training” is due at the end of the Ramp-Up Phase.

6. Mandatory presentation of results

Deliverable D.RUp.8 Short overview and presentation

At the end of the Ramp-Up Phase, a brief overview of the service and the results of the Ramp-Up Phase must be written. The text should summarise what their service provides in the end. Possible questions to ask could be:

- What progress has been made with respect to the finalisation of the service?
- Are there additional groups of service users and from which thematic contexts?
- What is the long-term perspective of the service?

This short report will be published as a news item on the Base4NFDI website. Alternatively, the service team can choose their own way of publishing a summary of their service development activities in the Ramp-Up Phase.

In addition, there must be a presentation of the Ramp-Up Phase results in a meeting of their respective section after the phase has ended.

Documentation:

- Both the report and the presentation must be documented (e. g., linked) in the OpenProject task of this deliverable.

Due date: The report must be submitted to the Base4NFDI office and TA3 no later than **6 weeks after the end of the Ramp-Up Phase**. The presentation must be given in the next section meeting after the end of the Ramp-up Phase.

If you publish your reports, please follow the [Base4NFDI publication policy](#) and the [Signalisation instructions Base4NFDI](#), and acknowledge both Base4NFDI and the funder DFG together with the funding number for basic services 521453681. It is also possible to use the Base4NFDI and DFG logos, which are available for download on this [website](#).

Deliverable D.RUp.9 Participation in Base4NFDI outreach events

Active participation with a presentation of the service, in the first place at the annual Base4NFDI User Conference, is mandatory during the Ramp-Up Phase. Participation in the Base4NFDI Demos or Service Roadshow is highly recommended.

Documentation:

- All presentations should be listed and linked in the OpenProject task of this deliverable.
- If events and educational resources are already listed elsewhere, there is no need to repeat this here, but the respective lists should be linked to the OpenProject task.

Due date: The OpenProject list must be up to date at the end of the Ramp-Up Phase.

Acknowledgements

Many of these concepts have been inspired by what HIFIS¹² (Helmholtz Federated IT Services) has built over recent years to bring services together in a standardised catalogue and manage them jointly. We would like to thank the HIFIS team for many fruitful and committed discussions.

¹² <https://hifs.net>